

science and policy
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Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results

Deliverable Report

D8.4

WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level

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Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marike KOLOSSA-GEHRING	UBA	14/08/2018
Grant Signatory	Greet Schoeters	VITO	13/08/2019

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Argelia Castaño	ISCIll	14/08/2018
Work Package Leader	Ovnair Sepai	PHE	13/08/2018
Task leader	Greet Schoeters	VITO	13/08/2018

Responsible author	Greet Schoeters	E-mail	Greet.schoeters@vito.be
Short name of institution	VITO	Phone	+32 14 33 51 67
Co-authors	Liese Gilles (VITO)		

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 2

Table of Contents

1	Authors and acknowledgements	3
2	Abstract	4
3	Introduction	5
4	Conditions for participation.....	6
4.1	Tasks to be fulfilled by participating countries	6
5	Overview of selected studies	8
5.1	Overview of focussed chemicals and age groups	8
5.2	Overview of participating studies per European region	8
5.3	Selected studies per age group and per country	10
5.4	Information per participating study	13
5.5	Overview of planned chemical analysis per study	17
5.6	List of first set of accessory variables.....	22
5.7	Influencing and interfering factors for sampling and sample storage	23

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 3

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Greet Schoeters (VITO)

Liese Gilles (VITO)

Contributors

Study Principal Investigators/ study contact persons: Gudrun Koppen (VITO), Nicole Probst-Hensch (SWISS TPH), Martin Zvonař (MU), Jana Klanova (MU), Lenka Andrýsková (MU), Nina Vogel (UBA), Marike Kolossa-Gehring (UBA), André Conrad (UBA), Till Weber (UBA), Tina Kold Jensen (SDU), Anna-Maria Andersson (RegionH), Anders Juul (RegionH), Hanne Frederiksen (RegionH), Denis Sarigiannis (AUTH), Argelia Castaño (ISCIII), Juan José Ramos (ISCIII) Susana Pedraza (ISCIII), Marta Esteban (ISCIII), Hanna Tolonen (THL), Hannu Kirivanta (THL), Loïc Rambaud (ANSP), Clemence Fillol (ANSP), Natasa Janev Holcer (CIPH), Tamás Szigeti (NPHI), Þórhallur Ingi Halldórsson (UI), Fabio Barbone (EPIUD), An van Nieuwenhuyse, Roel Vermeulen, Cathrine Thomsen (NIPH), Helle M. Meltzer (NIPH), Sónia Namorado (INSA), Marika Berglund (KI), Sanna Lignell (KI), Ľubica Murínová (SZU), Milena Horvat (JSI), Janja Snoj Tratnik (JSI), Wojciech Wasowicz (NIOM), Beata Janasik (NIOM)

Quality Assurance Unit: Argelia Castaño (ISCIII), Marta Esteban (ISCIII), Thomas Göen (IPASUM), Holger Koch (IPA), Monika Kasper-Sonnenberg (IPA), Daniel Bury (IPA), Jana Hajslova (VSCHT), Thomas Lund (ULUND), Cathrine Thomsen (NIPH), Line Småstuen Haug (NIPH), Katrin Vorkamp (AU), Jean Philippe Antignac (INRA), Adrian Covaci (UAntwerpen), Hanne Frederiksen (Region H), Jana Klanova (MU), Octavio Pérez (ULPGC), Jiri Kohoutek (MU), Petr Kukucka (MU), Lisa Melymuk (RECETOX)

And the Chemical Substance Group Leaders (CGLs): Rosa Lange (UBA), Robert Barouki (INSERM), Maria Uhl (EAA), Ingrid Hauzenberger (EAA), Jana Klánová (MU), Lisa Melymuk (RECETOX), Milena Horvat (JSI), Janja Snoj Tratnik (JSI), Alessandro Alimonti (ISS), Elena De Felip (ISS), Tiina Santonen (FIOH), Denis Sarigiannis (AUTH), Erik Lebret (RIVM), Mirjam Luijten (RIVM)

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 4

2 Abstract

The aim of Task 8.1 is to align ongoing/planned studies to collect HBM data of the prioritised chemicals with EU wide coverage. To realise this task a European sampling frame was developed. We started from a theoretical concept describing criteria related to recruitment and sampling to obtain current exposure data across Europe. Current exposure was hereby defined as samples taken between 2014 and 2019 i.e. over the last 5 years. This concept was then adapted to fit reality, e.g. it was decided to not only include national representative studies but also regional studies with a large catching area and to focus on 3 age groups instead of 5. The 3 age groups that were selected are: children (6-11 years), teenagers (12-19 years) and adults (20-39 years).

Within each age group the focus was placed on specific chemicals. For children the focus is on the analysis of phthalates/DINCH and flame retardants, for teenagers on phthalates/DINCH and per-poly- fluorinated compounds and for adults on cadmium, bisphenols and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH's).

The drafted proposal of eligible candidate studies was accepted by the HBM4EU Management Board and implementation will start from June 2018 onwards. Currently, 21 different countries, representing north, east, south and west Europe will participate in the sampling frame. This will result in chemical exposure data of 2950 children, 2900 teenagers and 3165 adults distributed across Europe. This will be an exciting first step towards a first EU wide HBM survey.

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 5

3 Introduction

To realise Task 8.1 we have established a sampling frame for Europe as explained in deliverable D8.1 “Description of national programs”. Based on the inventory resulting from the questionnaire of Task 7.1 data gaps on the first set of priority chemicals were identified and we invited national hubs and Principal Investigators (PI) from potentially eligible studies for bilateral telephone conferences to discuss opportunities for participation in the alignment of studies and potential hurdles. As a result of these discussions, we realised that adaptations to the theoretical sampling frame were needed to fit reality.

As a first step, due to the scarce availability of recent exposure data on the first set of priority chemicals and due to financial limitations, it was decided to focus on specific age groups and on specific chemicals per age group (see Table 1). As a second step it was decided that also regional studies with wide catching areas could be included into the sampling frame next to national representative studies. And to also accept smaller studies of 200-300 subjects if no alternative studies/options were available.

The resulting approach has been presented to the Governing Board, the Advisory Board, the Stakeholder Forum and several times at meetings of the HBM4EU Management Board. All studies that fit the sampling frame and that agreed with the conditions to participate were accepted to participate in the alignment of studies. This resulted in 33 studies from 21 different European countries that together will contribute to the first EU wide HBM survey.

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 6

4 Conditions for participation

Before eligible studies were accepted they had to meet the conditions for participation that were defined. Following requirements had to be met by the participating studies:

1. Samples are collected between 2014 and 2019 (last ± 5 years).
2. We aim to include 300 subjects (with a balanced sex-ratio males / females) per age slot and per participating EU region.
3. Sampling conditions and storage are matching specific technical requirements as specified by Work Package 9. Available in Table 9: Influencing and interfering factors in sampling and sample storage.
4. Willingness to measure the analytes specified for the first set of priority compounds per age group- list of analytes per substance group available in Table 7: list of analytes included in Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/QC) Scheme organised by Work Package 9.
5. The analysis should be performed in labs that successfully pass the Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/AC) Scheme organised by Work Package 9 in the second half of 2018- list of candidate labs see deliverable D9.3 "Database of candidate laboratories for the 1st prioritisation round of substances".
6. The exposure data should be made available as single measurement data before end of 2019 together with a set of accessory variables to the HBM4EU consortium via the HBM4EU repository and EU commission and member state authorities via the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (IPCHEM). First set of accessory variables are available in Table 8.
7. The ethical approvals of the studies as well as the permission to transfer the single measurement data for statistical analysis at EU level should be made available to the project coordinator as soon as the amendment is approved.
8. The studies have to comply with the HBM4EU data management plan and data policy see deliverable D10.1 "Data Management Plan".

4.1 Tasks to be fulfilled by participating countries

Ethical approval, fieldwork such as new sampling, making biobanked samples available, post-harmonisation of variables falls under Work Package 8 Task 8.1

All participating studies are required to send their ethics documentation to the coordinator in 2018 prior to the inclusion of their studies in the HBM4EU programme. This work will be supported by the ethics coordinator (Lisbeth Knudsen).

All participating studies will collect HBM samples or make biobanked samples available for analysis in the frame of HBM4EU. If not yet finalised in 2018, they can continue and finish their fieldwork operations or access biobanked samples in 2019. All studies will consider the materials for survey design developed by Work Package 7, and make use of them as much as possible. Available documents are deliverable D7.3 "1st prioritisation report on survey design: study protocols, SOPs and guidelines, tailored and transferred questionnaires for recruitment and sampling" and deliverable D7.4 "1st material for communication to participants, including informed consent".

All the partners that bring in HBM data will demonstrate that the chemical analysis have been done according to HBM4EU standards in HBM4EU qualified labs. All the partners will extract the requested personal variables from the questionnaires and make them available to HBM4EU together with the biomarker exposure data. The variables will be made available at the individual

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 7

level in a format prescribed by Work Package 10 before the end of 2019. This harmonised format and the HBM4EU data template ensures sharing of pseudonymised individual data. The data will be stored in the HBM4EU repository/IPCHEM. This work will be supported by Work Packages 7/8.

Transport and chemical analysis of samples in HBM4EU falls under Work Package 9 Task 9.5

All participating studies will analyse priority chemicals in their samples in HBM4EU qualified laboratories as indicated in Table 6. All partners will analyse basic parameters like creatinine for urinary samples (for all ages), specific gravity for urinary samples of teenagers and lipid measurement for fat soluble FR analysed in serum. If samples have to be shipped partners will send the samples according to the SOP's developed by Work Package 7 available in deliverable D7.2 "Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands". This work will be supported by Work Packages 7/9.

Processing of data and providing data to HBM4EU falls under Work Package 10 Task 10.6

All participating studies will share the co-funded exposure data and accompanying variables (see Table 8) at the individual level in a HBM4EU harmonised format prescribed by Work Package 10 before the end of 2019. This work includes: extraction of variables from their questionnaire and harmonising them according to HBM4EU developed codebook. This harmonised format and the HBM4EU data template ensures sharing of pseudonymised individual data. The data will be stored in the HBM4EU repository/IPCHEM. This work will be supported by Work Package 10.

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 8

5 Overview of selected studies

5.1 Overview of focussed chemicals and age groups

Due to the scarce availability of recent exposure data on the first set of priority chemicals and due to financial limitations it was decided to focus on specific chemicals per age group to achieve EU wide coverage of these focussed chemicals within the selected age groups.

Table 1: Overview of focussed chemicals per age group

Children 6-11 years	Teenagers 12-19 years	Adults 20-39 years
Phthalates + DINCH	Phthalates + DINCH	Bisphenols (A,S, F)
Brominated Flame retardants optional: Fluorinated/Chlorinated FR	Per/poly-fluorinated compounds	Occupational exposures: Cadmium and PAH

5.2 Overview of participating studies per European region

Currently **21 different European countries, representing north, east, south and west Europe, are participating in the alignment of studies.** This will result in chemical exposure data of 2950 children, 2900 teenagers and 3165 adults distributed across Europe. A summary overview of the participating countries is available in Table 2.

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 9

Table 2: Overview of studies selected to participate in the sampling frame

Geographical region of Europe	North		West		South		East		
% of European population ¹	21% ¹		40% ¹		28% ¹		11% ¹		
Minimal number of countries to be included per age	2 countries Aim: 600 participants		3-4 countries Aim: 900-1200 participants		3 countries Aim: 900 participants		1 country Aim: 300 participants		
EU Countries participating in HBM4EU and number of inhabitants (millions) ² : Countries participating in task 8.1 (have relevant sampling planned or samples/data sets available) Countries not participating in task 8.1 (have no planned or current sampling according to the criteria)	DK	5.75	AT	8.75	HR	4.16	CZ	10.63	
	FI	5.54	BE	11.50	CY	0.854	PL	38.10	
	SE	9.98	NL	17.08	EL	11.14	SK	5.45	
	IS	0.338	FR	65.23	IT	59.29	HU	9.69	
	NO	5.35	DE	82.30	PT	10.30			
	LV	1.93	CH	8.54	SI	2.08			
	LT	2.88	LU	0.590	ES	46.40			
	IE	4.80							
UK	66.57								
Children (6-11y)	Norway_NEBII Denmark_OCC Participants 600		France_ESTEBAN Germany_GerES V Netherlands_Dutch Youth cohort Participants 900		Slovenia_SLOCRP Greece_CROME Italy_NACII Participants 600 ³		Hungary_InAirQ Slovakia_PCB cohort Poland_POLAES Participants 850		Aim children: 2700-3000 Total Children: 2950
Adolescents (12-19y)	Sweden_Riksmaten Norway_NEBII Participants 500		France_ESTEBAN Belgium_FLEHS IV Germany_GerES V Participants 900		Slovenia_SLOCRP Greece_CROME Spain_BEA Participants 600 ³		Poland_POLAES Czech Republic_school children Slovakia_PCB cohort (follow-up) Participants 900		Aim Adolescents: 2700-3000 Total Adolescents: 2900
Adults (20-40y)	Denmark_CPHMINIPUB Iceland_Nutrition survey Finland_FinHealth Participants 800		France_ESTEBAN Switzerland_New Study Germany_ESB Luxembourg_New study Participants 1165		Croatia_CIPH Portugal_INSEF Participants 600 ³		Poland_POLAES CzechRepublic_ELSPAC Participants 600		Aim Adults: 2700-3000 Total Adults: 3165

¹ Based on United Nations geoscheme: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/United_Nations_geoscheme_for_Europe

² Based on <http://www.worldometers.info/population/countries-in-europe-by-population/> (consulted 13/08/2018)

³ In this region we do not reach the aimed number of participants.

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 10

5.3 Selected studies per age group and per country

The tables in this section provide a more detailed overview of the participating studies per age group. For the studies on children see Table 3, for the studies on teenagers see Table 4 and for the studies on adults see Table 5.

Table 3: Overview of studies included for new analysis of phthalates, DINCH and flame retardants in children

Age group: 6-11 years												
EU region	Country	Institute	Study	N° samples	Phthalates (urine)	DINCH (urine)	FR (urine)	FR (serum)	Specific age	M/F	Status study (C: collected, O: ongoing, P: planned)	National/Regional
North 21% 2 countries	Norway	NIPH	NEBII	300 urine 300 serum	✓	✓	✓	✓	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	M/F	C: 2016-... biobanked samples	National
	Denmark	SDU	OCC	300 urine	✓	✓	✓	✗	7	M/F	O: 2017-... new sample collection	Regional (Fyn region)
East 11% 1 country	Hungary	NPHI	InAirQ	264 urine	✓	✓	✗	✗	9, 10, 11	M/F	O: Nov 2017- March 2018 biobanked samples	National
	Slovakia	SZU	PCB cohort	300 urine	✓	✓	✓	✗	10, 11	M/F	C: 2014-2017 biobanked samples	National
	Poland	NIOM	POLAES	300 urine	✓	✓	✗	✗	7, 8, 9, 10, 11	M/F	O: 2017-... biobanked samples	Regional (Głogów)
South 28% 3 countries	Slovenia	JSI	SLOCRP	150 urine 150 serum	✓	✓	✗	✓	6,7,8,9	M/F	P: 2018 -2019 new sample collection	National
	Greece	AUTH	CROME (extension)	150 urine 150 blood	✓	✓	✗	✓	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	M/F	P: 2018- 2019 new sample collection	National
	Italy	EPIUD	NACII	300 urine	✓	✓	✗	✗	7	M/F	O: 2016-2018 new sample collection	Regional (Trieste)
West 40% 3-4 countries	France	ANSP	ESTEBAN	300 urine	✓	✓	✓	✓	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	M/F	C: 14/04/2014 - 31/03/2016 biobanked samples	National
	Germany	UBA	GerES V	300 urine 300 plasma	✓	✓	✓	✓	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11	M/F	C: 2015 - 2017 biobanked samples	National
	The Netherlands	IRAS/UU	Dutch Youth cohort	300 urine	✓	✓	✓	✗	8, 9, 10	M/F	P: 2018-2019 new sample collection	Regional (Province Utrecht)

✓: analysis of this substance (group) is included, ✗: analysis of this substance (group) is not included, √: analysis of this substance (group) was already planned outside HBM4EU, data will be shared with the project (only with consortium members and during project time).

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 11

Table 4: Overview of studies included for new analysis of phthalates, DINCH and per-/poly-fluorinated compounds in teenagers

Age groups: 12-19 years											
EU region	Country	Institute	Study	N° samples	Phthalates (urine)	DINCH (urine)	Per-/ Poly-fluorinated Compounds (serum)	Specific age	M/F	Status study (C: collected, O: ongoing, P: planned)	National/Regional
North 21% 2 countries	Sweden	SEPA	Riksmaten	300 urine 300 serum	✓	✓	✓	12, 16, 19	M/F	P: 2017-2018 biobanked samples	National
	Norway	NIPH	NEBII	184 urine 184 plasma	✓	✓	✓	12, 13, 14	M/F	C: 2016-... biobanked samples	National
East 11% 1 country	Poland	NIOM	POLAES	300 urine	✓	✓	✗	12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19	M/F	O: 2017-... biobanked samples	Regional (Głogów)
	Czech Republic	MU	Pilot study school children	300 urine	✓	✗	✗	12, 13, 14, 15	M/F	P: 2018 new sample collection	National (6 schools)
	Slovakia	SZU	PCB cohort (follow-up)	300 urine 300 serum	✓	✓	✓	14, 15, 16, 17	M/F	P: 2018-2019 New sample collection	National
South 28% 3 countries	Slovenia	JSI	SLOCRP	150 urine 150 serum	✓	✓	✓	12, 13, 14, 15	M/F	P: 2018 new sample collection	National
	Greece	AUTH	CROME (extension)	150 urine 150 blood	✓	✓	✓	12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19	M/F	P: 2018 new sample collection	National
	Spain	ISCI	BEA	300 urine 300 serum	✓	✓	✓	14, 15, 16	M/F	O: 1/09/2017-31/01/2018 biobanked samples	National
West 40% 3-4 countries	France	ANSP	ESTEBAN	300 urine	✓	✓	✓	12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19	M/F	31/03/2016 biobanked samples	National
	Belgium	VITO	FLEHS IV	300 urine 300 serum	✓	✓	✓	14, 15	M/F	P: 2018 new sample collection	Regional (Flanders)
	Germany	UBA	GerESV	300 urine	✓	✓	✓	12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17	M/F	C: 2015 - 2017 biobanked samples	National

✓: analysis of this substance (group) is included, ✗: analysis of this substance (group) is not included, ✓: analysis of this substance (group) was already planned outside HBM4EU, data will be shared with the project (only with consortium members and during project time).

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 12

Table 5: Overview of studies included for new analysis of bisphenols, cadmium and PAH in adults

Age groups: 20-39 years											
EU region	Country	Institute	Study	N° samples	Bisphenols (urine)	Cd (urine)	PAH (urine)	Specific age	M/F	Status study (C: collected, O: ongoing, P: planned)	National/Regional
North 21% 2 countries	Denmark	RegionH	CPHMINIPUB (parents)	300 urine	√	√	√	N.A.	M/F	P: 2018 - 2019 new sample collection	Regional
	Iceland	UI	Nutrition Survey	200 urine 200 blood	√	√	√	N.A.	M/F	P: 2018 - 2019 new sample collection	National
	Finland	THL	FinHealth	300 urine	√	X	X	N.A.	M/F	C: 01/2017 - 07/2017 biobanked samples	National
East 11% 1 country	Poland	NIOM	POLAES	300 urine	√	√	√	N.A.	M/F	O: 2017-... biobanked samples	Regional (Głogów)
	Czech Republic	MU	ELSPAC	300 urine 300 blood	√	√	√	26, 27, 28	M/F	P: 2018 - 2019 new sample collection	Regional
South 28% 3 countries	Croatia	CIPH	Human Biomonitoring Survey in Adults in	300 urine 300 blood	√	√	√	N.A.	M/F	P: 2018 - 2019 new sample collection	National
	Portugal	INSA	INSEF	300 urine	√	√	(√)	N.A.	M/F	P: 2018 - 2019 new sample collection	National
West 40% 3-4 countries	France	ANSP	ESTEBAN	300 urine	√	√	√	N.A.	M/F	C: 14/04/2014 - 31/03/2016 biobanked samples	National
	Switzerland	SWISS TPH	New Study	300 urine	√	(√)	(√)	N.A.	M/F	P: 2019 new sample collection	Regional Basel-Stadt/Basel-Land/ Vaud
	Luxembourg	LNS/LIST/LIH	New study	265 urine	√	√	(√)	N.A.	M/F	C: N.A. (2014-2018) biobanked samples	N.A.
	Germany	UBA	ESB	300 urine	X	√	√	20-29	M/F	C: 2014-2016-2018 Biobanked samples	Regional (4 cities)

√: analysis of this substance (group) is included, x: analysis of this substance (group) is not included, (√): analysis of this substance (group) is uncertain, √: analysis of this substance (group) was already planned outside HBM4EU, data will be shared with the project (only with consortium members and during project time).

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 13

5.4 Information per participating study

In this section a description of the work expected to be done per study is provided.

All the partners participating in the alignment of studies are committed to:

- i) Collect HBM samples or make biobanked samples available for analysis in the HBM4EU project.
- ii) Transport samples to lab + analyse priority chemicals in their samples in HBM4EU qualified laboratories as indicated in Table 6. All partners will analyse basic parameters like creatinine for urinary samples (for all ages), specific gravity for urinary samples of teenagers and lipid measurement for fat soluble flame retardants analysed in serum. If samples have to be shipped partners commit to send the samples according to the SOP's developed by Work Package 7.
- iii) Share the co-funded exposure data and accompanying variables (see Table 8) at the individual level in a HBM4EU harmonised format prescribed by Work Package 10 before the end of 2019. This work includes: extraction of variables from their questionnaire and harmonising them according to HBM4EU developed codebook. This harmonised format and the HBM4EU data template ensures sharing of individual data. The data will be stored in the HBM4EU repository/IPCHEM.

Children - Making biobanked samples available

NIPH-NEBII

NIPH will make 300 biobanked urine samples and 300 biobanked plasma samples available from children (boys and girls, 6-11 years) stored in the Norwegian Environmental Biobank. NIPH will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites, DINCH, flame retardants in urine.

SZU-PCB cohort

SZU will make 300 biobanked urine samples available from children (boys and girls, 10-11 years) participating in the PCB cohort. SZU will make these samples available for analysis of DINCH and flame retardants in urine. In addition SZU will make exposure data on phthalate metabolites available.

NPHI-InAirQ

NPHI will make 264 biobanked urine samples available from children (boys and girls, 9-11 years) participating in the InAirQ study. NPHI will make these samples available for analysis of Phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine under the condition they successfully participate in QA/QC.

NIOM-PLAES

NIOM will make 300 biobanked urine samples available from children (boys and girls, 7-11 years) participating in the POLAES study. NIOM will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine.

ANSP-ESTEBAN

ANSP will make 300 biobanked urine and 300 biobanked serum samples available from children (boys and girls, 6-11 years) participating in the national ESTEBAN study. ANSP will analyse phthalate metabolites, DINCH, flame retardants in urine and flame retardants in serum.

UBA-GerES V

UBA will make 300 biobanked urine and 300 biobanked plasma samples available from children (boys and girls, 6-11 years) participating in the national GerES V study. UBA will analyse flame retardants in urine and flame retardants in plasma. In addition UBA will make exposure data on phthalate metabolites and DINCH available.

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 14

Children - New sample collection

SDU-OCC

SDU will collect 300 urine samples from children (boys and girls, 7 years) participating in the Odense Child Cohort study. SDU will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites, DINCH and flame retardants in urine.

EPIUD-NACII

EPIUD will collect 300 urine samples from children (boys and girls, 7 years) participating in the NACII study. EPIUD will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine.

IRAS-Dutch Youth Cohort

IRAS will collect 300 urine samples from children (boys and girls, 8-10 years) participating in the Dutch Youth Cohort. IRAS will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites, DINCH and flame retardants in urine.

JSI-SLOCRP

JSI will collect 150 urine and 150 serum samples from children (boys and girls, 6-9 years) participating in the SLOCRP study. JSI will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites, DINCH and flame retardants in urine and flame retardants in serum.

AUTH-CROME

AUTH will collect 150 urine and 150 serum samples from children (boys and girls, 6-11 years) participating in the CROME study. AUTH will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine and flame retardants in serum.

Teenagers - Making biobanked samples available

NIPH-NEBII

NIPH will make 184 biobanked urine and 184 biobanked plasma samples available from teenagers (boys and girls, 12-14 years) stored in the Norwegian Environmental Biobank. NIPH will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine and per-/poly- fluorinated compounds in plasma.

SEPA-Riksmaten

SEPA will make 300 biobanked urine and 300 biobanked serum samples available from teenagers (boys and girls, 12,16,19 years) participating in the Riksmaten study. SEPA will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine and per-/poly- fluorinated compounds in serum.

NIOM-POLAES

NIOM will make 300 biobanked urine samples available from teenagers (boys and girls, 12-19 years) participating in the POLAES study. NIOM will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine.

ANSP-ESTEBAN

ANSP will make 300 biobanked urine samples available from teenagers (boys and girls, 12-19 years) participating in the ESTEBAN study. ANSP will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine. In addition ANSP will provide data of exposure to per-/poly- fluorinated compounds.

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 15

Teenagers - New sample collection

ISCI-III-BEA

ISCI-III will collect 300 urine and 300 serum samples from teenagers (boys and girls, 14-16 years) participating in the national BEA study. ISCI-III will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine and per-/poly-fluorinated compounds in serum.

VITO-FLEHS IV

VITO will collect 300 urine and 300 serum samples from teenagers (boys and girls, 14-15 years) participating in the FLEHS IV study. VITO will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine and per-/poly-fluorinated compounds in serum.

SZU-PCB cohort (follow-up)

SZU will collect 300 urine and 300 serum samples from teenagers (boys and girls, 10-11 years) participating in the PCB cohort follow-up. SZU will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites and DINCH in urine and per-/poly-fluorinated compounds in serum.

JSI-SLOCRP

JSI will collect 150 urine and 150 serum samples from teenagers (boys and girls, 12-15 years) participating in the SLOCRP study. JSI will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites, DINCH in urine and per-/poly-fluorinated compounds in serum.

AUTH-CROME

AUTH will collect 150 urine and 150 serum samples from teenagers (boys and girls, 12-15 years) participating in the CROME study. AUTH will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites, DINCH in urine and per-/poly-fluorinated compounds in serum.

MU-Pilot study in school children

MU will collect 300 urine samples from teenagers (boys and girls, 12-15 years) participating in the pilot study on school children. MU will make these samples available for analysis of phthalate metabolites in urine.

Teenagers - making data available

UBA-GerES V

UBA will provide data of exposure to phthalate metabolites and DINCH and per-/poly-fluorinated compound in teenagers (boys and girls, 12-17 years) participating in the GerES V study.

Adults - Making biobanked samples available

THL-Finhealth

THL will make 300 biobanked urine samples available from adults (males and females, 20-39 years) that participated in the national Finhealth study. THL will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols (THL-lab).

NIOM-POLAES

NIOM will make 300 biobanked urine samples available from adults (males and females, 20-39 years) that participated in the POLAES study. NIOM will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols, cadmium and PAH.

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 16

LNS-New study

LNS will make 265 biobanked urine samples available from adults (males and females, 20-39 years). LNS will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols and cadmium. *Optional measurements PAH in urine (not confirmed yet⁴).*

UBA-ESB

UBA will make 300 biobanked urine samples available from adults (males and females, 20-29 years) that participated in the environmental specimen bank (ESB) study. UBA will make these samples available for analysis of cadmium and PAH.

Adults - New sample collection

UI-Nutrition survey

UI will collect 200 urine and 200 blood samples from adults (males and females, 20-39 years) participating in the Nutrition survey. UI will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols, cadmium and PAH in urine.

MU-ELSPAC

MU will collect 300 urine and 300 blood samples from adults (males and females, 26-28 years) participating in the ELSPAC study. MU will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols, cadmium and PAH in urine.

CIPH-Implementation of Human Biomonitoring Survey in Adults in Croatia Using HBM4EU Methodology

CIPH will collect 300 urine and 300 blood samples from randomly selected male and female adults (20-39 years) participating in the "Implementation of Human Biomonitoring Survey in Adults in Croatia Using HBM4EU Methodology". CIPH will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols, cd and PAH in urine.

RegionH-CPHMINIPUB (parents)

RegionH will collect 300 urine samples from adults (males and females, 20-39 years) participating in the CPHMINIPUB study. RegionH will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols, cadmium and PAH in urine.

SWISS TPH-New study

SWISS TPH will collect 300 urine and 300 blood samples from adults (males and females, 20-39 years) participating in the Swiss National Health Study. SWISS TPH will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols in urine. *Optional measurements cadmium and PAH in urine (not confirmed yet).*

INSA-INSEF

INSA will collect 300 urine samples from adults (males and females, 28-39 years) participating in the National Health Examination Survey. INSA will make these samples available for analysis of bisphenols and cadmium in urine. *Optional measurements PAH in urine (not confirmed yet⁴).*

Adults - making data available

ANSP-ESTEBAN

ANSP will provide data of exposure to bisphenols, cadmium and PAH in adults (20-39 years).

⁴ If the amount to pay for the analyses of the samples is less than expected and the budget allows it, analyses of PAHs will also be performed.

5.5 Overview of planned chemical analysis per study

Table 6 provides an overview of the planned chemical analysis per study on substance group level. The study centres have indicated they intend to measure all metabolites as listed in Table 7 for the selected substance groups. However, the actual metabolites that will be measured will depend on the analytical capacity of the QAQC qualified labs.

Table 6: Planned chemical analysis of 1st set of prioritised substances in aligned studies.

	Children			Teenagers			Adults			
	Urine		Serum	Urine		Serum	Urine			
Partner	Phthalates	DINCH	Flame retardants	Flame retardants	Phthalates	DINCH	Per-fluorinated Compounds	Bisphenol	Cadmium	PAH
VITO					√	√	√			
UI								√	√	√
UBA	(√) ⁵	(√) ⁵	√	√ ⁶	(√) ⁵	(√) ⁵	(√) ⁵		√	√
THL								√		
SZU	(√) ⁷	√	√		√	√	√			
Swiss TPH								√	(√) ⁸	(√) ⁸
SEPA					√	√	√			
SDU	√	√	√							
RegionH								√	√	√
NPHI ⁹	√	√								
NIPH	√	√	√	√	√	√	√			
NIOM	√	√			√	√		√	√	√

⁵ Phthalates and DINCH (in children) and phthalates, DINCH and Perfluorinated compounds (in adolescents) were already measured in GerES V samples, no new analysis will be performed but data will be provided.

⁶ Flame retardants will be analysed in plasma not in serum.

⁷ phthalates were already measured, no new analysis will be performed but data will be provided.

⁸ Analysis of cadmium and PAH not yet confirmed "will attempt to also obtain bio-specimens for measuring Cd and PAH exposure".

⁹ Phthalates and DINCH will be analysed under the condition they successfully pass QAQC.

	Children				Teenagers			Adults		
	Urine			Serum	Urine		Serum	Urine		
Partner	Phthalates	DINCH	Flame retardants	Flame retardants	Phthalates	DINCH	Per-fluorinated Compounds	Bisphenol	Cadmium	PAH
MU					√			√	√	√
LNS								√	√	√
JSI	√	√	√	√	√	√	√			
ISCIH					√	√	√			
IRAS	√	√	√							
INSA								√	√	√
EPIUD	√	√								
CIPH								√	√	√
AUTH	√	√		√	√	√	√			
ANSP	√	√	√	√	√	√	(√) ¹⁰	(√) ¹⁰	(√) ¹⁰	(√) ¹⁰

¹⁰ Perfluorinated compounds (in adolescents) and bisphenols, cadmium and PAH (in adults) were already measured in ESTEBAN study, no new analysis will be performed but data will be provided.

Table 7: List of analytes included in QAQC programme organised by Work Package 9

Analytes included in QAQC programme organised by Work Package 9			
Parent compound	Metabolites	Category ¹¹	Matrix
phthalates			
DEHP	MEHP	A	Urine
	5OH-MEHP	A	Urine
	5oxo-MEHP	A	Urine
	5cx-MEPP	A	Urine
DEP	MEP	A	Urine
BBzP	MBzP	A	Urine
DiBP	MiBP	A	Urine
DnBP	MnBP	A	Urine
DCHP	MCHP	B	Urine
DnPeP	MnPeP	B	Urine
DnOP	MnOP	B	Urine
DiNP	OH-MiNP	B	Urine
	cx-MiNP	B	Urine
DiDP	OH-MiDP	B	Urine
	cx-MiDP	B	Urine
DINCH			
DINCH	OH-MINCH	B	Urine
	cx-MINCH	B	Urine
Bisphenols			
	BPA	A	Urine
	BPF	B	Urine
	BPS	B	Urine
Per-poly fluorinated compounds			
	PFPeA	A	Serum
	PFHxA	A	Serum
	PFHpA	A	Serum
	PFOA	A	Serum
	PFNA	A	Serum
	PFDA	A	Serum
	PFUnDA	A	Serum
	PFDoDA	A	Serum
	PFBS	A	Serum
	PFHxS	A	Serum
	PFHpS	A	Serum
	PFOS (sum of all isomers)	A	Serum
PAHs			
(NAPH) naphthalene	1-hydroxynaphthalene	B	Urine

¹¹ Categorisation adopted from scoping documents

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 20

Analytes included in QAQC programme organised by Work Package 9			
Parent compound	Metabolites	Category ¹¹	Matrix
	2-hydroxynaphthalene	B	Urine
	1,2-dihydroxynaphthalene	B	Urine
Fluorene (FLUO)	2-hydroxyfluorene (2-FLUO)	B	Urine
	3-hydroxyfluorene (3-FLUO)	B	Urine
	9-hydroxyfluorene (9-FLUO)	B	Urine
(PHE) phenanthrene	1-hydroxyphenanthrene	B	Urine
	2-hydroxyphenanthrene	B	Urine
	3-hydroxyphenanthrene	B	Urine
	4-hydroxyphenanthrene	B	Urine
	9-hydroxyphenanthrene	B	Urine
Pyrene (PYR)	1-hydroxypyrene (1-PYR)	B	Urine
Benzo(a)pyrene	3-hydroxybenzo(a)pyrene	B	Urine
Flame Retardents			
PBDE's	BDE-47	A	Serum
	BDE-153	A	Serum
	BDE-209	A	Serum
HBCD's	α-HBCD	A	Serum
	γ-HBCD	A	Serum
	DPHP	?	Urine
	BDCIPP	?	Urine
	BCEP	?	Urine
	BCIPP	?	Urine
	TBBPA	B	Urine
	Syn-DP	B	Serum
	Anti-DP	B	Serum
	DBDPE	B	Serum
	2,4,6-Tribromo-phenol	C	Serum
Annilines			
	MDA	A	Urine
	MOCA	A	Urine
Anilin	Aniline	B	Urine
	p-aminophenol	B	Urine
	N-acetyl-4-aminophenol	?	Urine
	o-toluidine	B	Urine
	p-PDA	C	Urine
4TDA	2,4-TDA	C	Urine
6TDA	2,6-TDA	C	Urine
Cadmium			
	Cadmium	A	Urine

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 21

Analytes included in QAQC programme organised by Work Package 9			
Parent compound	Metabolites	Category ¹¹	Matrix
	Cadmium	A	Blood
Chromium			
	Total Chromium	C	Red blood cells (erythrocytes)
	Total Chromium	C	Urine
	Total Chromium	C	Plasma

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 22

5.6 List of first set of accessory variables

For proper interpretation of the HBM data a set of accessory variables such as age and sex are needed and have to be provided by the participating studies. Each study will share information needed to enable their data to be transferred to IPCHEM and to facilitate the reporting obligations; this may be done via the questionnaire in Task 7.1 or via a bespoke reporting template produced by Task 8.1. This information is needed at the individual subject level. A list of the minimal variables that are needed are provided in Table 8. Depending on the measured chemical, additional accessory variables can be requested. Work Package 10 is developing a codebook to harmonise the HBM data. Variables need to be delivered in the format indicated in the codebook. The codebook is available on the HBM4EU website: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/data-management/#squelch-taas-accordion-shortcode-content-5>.

Table 8: Minimal list of variables needed for each included study participant

Minimal list of accessory variables	
Analytical information	
Exposure concentrations	
Limit of detection (LOD)	
Limit of quantification (LOQ)	
Analytical method used	
Sampling info	
Matrix	
Sampling year	
Sampling month	
Sampling day	
Sampling season	
In case of blood or milk:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lipid content (required for fat soluble substances)
In case of urine:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creatinine concentration (required for <u>all age groups</u>)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific gravity (only required for adolescents)
Subject information	
Sex	
Age:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For children/adolescents in months
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For adults in years
ISCED of subject For children/adolescents ISCED of mother/father/household	
Smoking status of subject For children/adolescents: smoking status of parents	
Height	
Weight	
BMI	
Degree of urbanisation http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/work/2014_01_new_urban.pdf	
Country	
NUTS level of residence of the subject. NUTS (1, 2 and 3) http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/nuts-maps-.pdf or subdivision (if NUTS not available for that country) ISO 3166-2 CODE from https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search/code/	

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 23

5.7 Influencing and interfering factors for sampling and sample storage

For each substance (group) a set of recommendations were made to avoid sample contamination or inappropriate storage conditions that may influence the sample quality and hence the outcome of the biomarker analysis. Recommendations were made based on consultation of expert partners in Work Package 9 to ensure appropriate storage and transport of the samples. A summary of the recommendations is available in Table 9 adopted from deliverable D7.3. Annex 2.2.3. Standard Operating Procedure Templates. SOP 3 - Procedure for sampling human samples.

Table 9: Recommendations to control influencing and interfering factors in sampling and sample storage

Recommendations	Group of substances			
	Phthalates	DINCH	Bisphenols	FRs
Sampling material				
<i>To avoid</i>	- Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	- Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	- Polycarbonate (PC), polyethersulfone (PES), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), epoxy resins	–
<i>Preferred</i>	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)
<i>Pre-treatment</i>	- Wash with methanol - Decontamination with acid solution	–	–	- Material free of dust particles (rinse with methanol)
<i>Additives</i>	- No	- No	- No	- No
<i>Risk of contamination</i>	- Low/medium	- Low	- Low/medium	- Medium/high
<i>Precautions to minimise contamination</i>	- Precaution with non-oxidized monoester metabolites (MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP; MnPeP, MEHP, MnOP): take sampling blanks to account for onsite background values. - SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material.	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of field blanks	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks	- Avoid the use of polystyrene (PS) packaging boxes - Be aware of dust as major source of contamination - SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 24

Recommendations	Group of substances			
	Phthalates	DINCH	Bisphenols	FRs
Transport & conservation				
<i>Shipment</i>	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen If not cooling, not longer than 72h	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen If not cooling, not longer than 72h	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen - - Avoid transport in polystyrene (PS) packaging boxes
<i>Biobank</i>	- Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	- Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	- Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	- Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C Preferred - Avoid polystyrene (PS) boxes
Related questions				
<i>Medical treatment</i>	- Are you taking medication in plastic capsules? - Please list the medications used - Dialysis, blood transfusion, blood donations (prior 24h)	- Are you taking medication in plastic capsules? - Please list the medications used - Dialysis, blood transfusion, blood donations (prior 24h)	- Dental fillings and inlays	
<i>Diet</i>	- Fasting period in the last 24h - Please mention if the food was packed and/or warmed in plastic containers	- Fasting period in the last 24h - Please mention if the food was packed and/or warmed in plastic containers	- Are you eating regularly canned food?/ Are you drinking regularly beverages canned? - Last meal eating canned food/beverages - Please mention if the food was packed and/or warmed in plastic containers	- Fatty fish consumption (BFRs)
<i>Others</i>				- Occupation - Use of computer and electronic equipment * Note: FRs are a very diverse group and there is a large number of possible sources of exposure

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 25

Recommendations	Group of substances			
	PFAS	PAHs	Anilines	Cd & Cr
Sampling material				
<i>To avoid</i>	- Teflon (Polytetrafluoroethylene, PTFE) and other fluoropolymers, glass	–	–	- Glass and metal
<i>Preferred</i>	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Urine: Polypropylene (PP) - Blood: special tubes for trace elements analysis
<i>Pre-treatment</i>	- No	- No	–	Urine: wash sampling material with 10% solution of HNO ₃
<i>Additives</i>	- No	- No	- As precautionary measure, 0.5 g citric acid per 100 mL urine should be added to each sample container to avoid absorption of MDA, 2,4-/2,6-TDA.	- EDTA or heparin
<i>Risk of contamination</i>	- Medium	- Low	- High for aniline and o-toluidine	- Medium
<i>Precautions to minimise contamination</i>	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks - Precaution with dust particles	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material (including needles used in venipuncture), use of sampling blanks

D8.4 - Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe and preliminary results	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Greet Schoeters et al.	Page: 26

Recommendations	Group of substances			
	PFAS	PAHs	Anilines	Cd & Cr
Transport & conservation				
<i>Shipment</i>	Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen	Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen	Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen
				- Plasma: centrifugation and plasma removing is needed latest 24h after sampling - Red blood cells: centrifugation, plasma removing and three times washing with 0.9% NaCl solution is needed latest 24h after sampling
<i>Biobank</i>	Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred in PP material pre-treated with 10% solution of HNO ₃
Related questions				
<i>Medical treatment</i>	—	—	Recent use of acetaminophen, paracetamol, panodil	- Medication, contrast procedures in the pas 96h (Cr)
<i>Diet</i>	- Food eaten previous to the sampling - Consumption of microwave popcorn and packed fast food	- Barbeque	—	- Seafood consumption, canned food and drinks, vitamins and supplements containing Cr
<i>Others</i>	- Use of cosmetics, houseware, cleaning products, kitchen utensils, baking paper	- Smoking behaviour, black tattoos, traffic related exposure, occupational	- Smoking habits, occupational or environmental contact to isocyanate containing foams or glues and pesticides, hair dyes, tattoos.	- Smoking habits, occupation, piercing, jewelry, tattoos, implant, prothesis,